

FSE - SEET 2025

Start of Block: Consent + Introduction

Did you know that per LinkedIn data, approximately 1 in 24 NC State CSC graduates go into Product Management or a similar role? We are trying to learn more about what skills those graduates need! If you are a PM, or you work with PMs, we want your feedback! Please take a few minutes to fill out this short survey. **Consent Form Title of Study:** Educational and Practical Considerations of Software Product Management **IRB Protocol:** 26812 **Principal Investigator(s):** Hannah Estes, hместes@ncsu.edu **Funding Source:** National Science Foundation **NC State Faculty Point of Contact:** Kathryn Stolee, ktstolee@ncsu.edu You are being asked to complete a survey for research purposes. The survey concerns perceptions and opinions on software product management education and practice. You can expect that the survey will take roughly 5 to 15 minutes. You must be 18 years of age or older and employed at a company within the software industry to participate in this study. For this study, you will take one survey asking for your thoughts on software product managers. Completing this survey is voluntary; you can stop at any time by not continuing or exiting the survey at any time. We suggest you take this survey using a private device, in a private location, and a web browser set to private/incognito mode. If you choose to include your email address, it will be separated from your other responses. The data collected about you from this survey will be stored in accordance with NC State data protection standards. You will not receive any payment for completing this survey.

Click here for additional information concerning the European Economic Area (EEA) and the GDPR

If you are physically in the European Economic Area (EEA) The GDPR is a European law that details conditions under which it is lawful to collect, use, disclose, or process personal data. For this research project, the information collected is your email, however this is optional. Hannah Estes is collecting this data, and you can find their contact information at the top of this form. This information is collected by the questionnaire. The reason this is being collected is for future contact or follow-ups. One lawful basis for doing so is your consent. The information will be used for 2 years and will be used for research purposes. The data will be stored for 5 years and will be shared only with the research team, who are listed above. The information will not be shared with someone in another country under the lawful basis of your consent and the legitimate interest of research. If the data is shared, it will be shared in a completely de-identified format. The effect of the collection of this data to you is minimal. The use of your information is unlikely to cause harm to you. If you would like to request access to the information from this project about you, rectify the information about you, or remove all of your

information from this research project, you may do so by contacting the researcher named above unless it is impossible to identify your information amongst the other data. The EEA representative that you may contact is Kathryn Stolee, at ktstolee@ncsu.edu. Right to withdraw your participation Your participation is voluntary. Even if you agree initially, consent is an ongoing process. You can stop participating at any time for any reason. To do so, simply close out the tab in which the survey is on. You can also contact the student researcher Hannah Estes at hmestes@ncsu.edu. Or you can contact the faculty advisor for this research, Kathryn Stolee, at ktstolee@ncsu.ed.

If you have any questions about the survey, its implementation, or the research study, please contact the student researcher, Hannah Estes, at hmestes@ncsu.edu. You can also contact the faculty advisor for this research, Kathryn Stolee, at ktstolee@ncsu.edu. Please reference study number 26812 when contacting anyone about this project. If you have questions about your rights as a participant or are concerned with your treatment throughout the research process, please contact the NC State University IRB Director at IRB-Director@ncsu.edu, 919-515-8754, or fill out a confidential form online at <https://research.ncsu.edu/administration/compliance/research-compliance/irb/irb-forms-and-templates/participant-concern-and-complaint-form/> If you consent, please continue to the survey by clicking the next button.

Are you a bot? If not, check box!

End of Block: Consent + Introduction

Start of Block: Role Identification

Within the software industry, are you in a more product-focused or engineering-focused role?

- Product-focused (e.g., software product manager, technical product manager, user experience) (1)
- Engineering-focused (e.g., software engineer, engineering manager, data scientist, technical program manager) (2)
- Neither / I'm not in the software industry (3)

Skip To: End of Survey If Within the software industry, are you in a more product-focused or engineering-focused role? = Neither / I'm not in the software industry

Skip To: All Participants If Within the software industry, are you in a more product-focused or engineering-focused role? = Engineering-focused (e.g., software engineer, engineering manager, data scientist, technical program manager)

End of Block: Role Identification

Start of Block: Product Questions

Suppose an educator is designing an undergraduate course to teach software product management to computer science majors. Based on your experience, what topics, skills, or abilities should be taught? Why is each important to your profession?

First Topic/Skill/Ability:

Topic/Skill/Ability (1) _____

Why do you want to know? (2)

Second Topic/Skill/Ability:

Topic/Skill/Ability (1) _____

Why do you want to know? (2)

Third Topic/Skill/Ability:

Topic/Skill/Ability (1) _____

Why do you want to know? (2)

Fourth Topic/Skill/Ability:

Topic/Skill/Ability (1) _____

Why do you want to know? (2)

Fifth Topic/Skill/Ability:

Topic/Skill/Ability (1) _____

Why do you want to know? (2)

End of Block: Product Questions

Start of Block: All Participants

What is the **most valuable thing** a software product manager provides for software engineering teams?

End of Block: All Participants

Start of Block: Demographic

What is the highest extent of your formal education?

- High school, GED, or less (1)
 - Some college but no degree (2)
 - Vocational or trade training (3)
 - Associate's or 2-year degree (4)
 - Bachelor's or 4-year degree (5)
 - Professional degree (6)
 - Master's degree (7)
 - Doctorate degree (8)
 - Prefer not to say (9)
-

(Optional) What company do you work for?

How long have you been in your profession?

- Less than 1 year (1)
 - 1-3 years (2)
 - 3-5 years (3)
 - 5-10 years (4)
 - 10+ years (5)
 - Prefer not to say (6)
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What is your gender identity? (Select all that apply)

Female (1)

Male (2)

Non-binary (5)

Prefer to self-identify (3)

Prefer not to say (4)

Page Break

(Optional) Are you comfortable sharing your email address to receive the results of this study or for potential follow-up communication? If so, please provide your email address below.

(Optional) Would you like to provide any feedback on the survey?

End of Block: Demographic
